

How to bring innovation and improvement for worldwide SME purchasing and supply chain processes. How can we develop big Aviation businesses by using the Blockchain?

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The GSC Aviation Marketplace aims to create a virtuous circle of relationships between purchasers and suppliers globally.

2. Aim

GSC Aviation aims to reduce the time and cost typically associated with transactional purchasing activities and thus allow procurement teams to focus on strategic value creation within their organizations. Additionally, the GSC platform will introduce European and North American suppliers to potential customers from emergent aviation markets like the Middle-East, Africa and Asia.

3. Material and methods

Custom web and app based tools utilizing blockchain technology will streamline purchasing activities through an event driven process which directly engages suppliers. Detailed vendor profiles within the platform will enable buyers to discover and quickly integrate vetted suppliers into their resource pool. An e-sourcing module with spare parts and services provided by referenced suppliers will ensure purchasers are engaging suppliers that meet or exceed all regulatory requirements.

A simplified rating system akin to ‘Trip Advisor’ will allow purchasers to rate and review suppliers following a RFQ (Request For Quotation). The rating process will give purchasers a quick overview during and after the RFQ process highlighting suppliers from most to least relevant.

Additionally, suppliers will enrich the GSC database by providing their own reviews of buyers based on criteria that is important to them such as financial stability and timely receipt of payment.

Finally, at the heart of the entire platform is the GSC Aviation Blockchain and its associated ERC20 Token. Among other capabilities, the GSC Blockchain will provide an

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authoritative and immutable record of traceability for all parts installed on every aircraft. The GSC Aviation Blockchain will enable buyers and suppliers to access critical historical information relating to the shelf life limit and limited potential of every part. From the date of manufacture to retirement. The associated data of each part will be securely stored and uniquely identifiable within the GSC Blockchain through the use of Hashlinks

4. Results

GSC's first milestone involves the creation of its informational website targeting potential investors and developers. Additionally, GSC aims to create a MVP web application for two aviation partners. The MVP web application will showcase its primary features and facilitate a feedback cycle for discovery and continuous development of the proposed platform.

5. Conclusions

GSC Aviation will create the perfect ecosystem to improve flight safety, aviation business operation, as well as saving time and money thanks to tools and blockchain tech dedicated to purchasers and suppliers.

6. Keywords

Blockchain Marketplace, Flight Safety, Supply Chain, Procurement, Industries, Predictive Maintenance

Author biography

Maxime Legros Maxime Legros He has been working in the aerospace sector as a buyer for over 7 years. Curious, strategist, comfortable in relationships, he enjoys teamwork and project management.

Passionate about his job, he has developed skills through experience and has decided to resume his studies at age 33 to pass a professional degree of Industrial Purchaser/Supply Chain Management alternately.

Once graduated from his degree in Purchasing and after started to give interest to the Blockchain and cryptocurrencies (in March 2017) and during a lunch with some US and UK suppliers, the GSC Aviation idea was born.

Richard Williams Richard Williams A long time internet enthusiast and web developer, Richard's first start up was an entertainment based website offering .mp2 encoded music for download in 1994. Richard has been involved in a number of successful web based ventures and has worked with fortune 100 companies like Microsoft and Comcast. Richard is the President and Co-founder of Wifidelity, a boutique .Net web development company. Wifidelity has developed and is currently licensing a Procurement data and tools platform to a successful membership based website. Richard became interested in blockchain in 2013 and has experience in Ethereum (Solidity) smart contract development.

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